

CERTIFICATE

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

Raximov Umidjon

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALIDA

THE INTERACTION BETWEEN THE PRODUCT TO BE GROUND AND THE GRINDING

BLADE IN THE GRINDING CHAMBER

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir: A.A. Abdurahmonov

Яндекс

@mail

Google

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